

Supplementary file 3. IGV screenshots of the read alignment of strains CBS 2916 (clade 1.2), CBS 10747 (clade 1.1) and CP367 (clade 1.1) in *C. metapsilosis* genome assembly.

a) Different boundaries between the clades 1.1 and 1.2 in the recombination event in *C. metapsilosis* *MAT* locus.

b) LOH blocks shared by clades 1.1 and 1.2 of *C. metapsilosis* covering the *MTC5* gene (g25)

c) LOH blocks shared by clades 1.1 and 1.2 of *C. metapsilosis* covering the *BPH1* gene (g211)

